

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article reflects the main direction and methodology of organizing project activities for students of non-language majors, traditional and active forms of interaction between teachers and students during the implementation of language projects in English. the concept of expanded.

Key words: project activities, forms of active education. language competence, method of organizing lessons.

The peculiarity of studying foreign languages (most often English) by non-native students in secondary schools and universities is that most of these students have unstable motivation and low level of foreign language proficiency. In this regard, teachers feel the need, on the one hand, to ensure communicative competence as the leading linguistic goal of education, and on the other hand, to organize and conduct lessons on language materials available to these listeners. Therefore, taking into account the specific characteristics of the chosen direction, it is necessary to rely on the existing personal experience of students, to implement important types of language activities in foreign language classes: speaking, reading and writing, gradually improving vocabulary knowledge on professional topics. slow expansion.

When planning the curriculum, it is necessary to take into account the choice of language topics, paying attention to the environment of young people, the peculiarities of their social relations, access to information resources, which not only increases motivation, but also improves communication between the teacher and students. makes it more open and modern, which allows to form interest in real materials in the future. For example. You can include "youth and society", "mass media", "talk shows and television news in the country of the language being studied" and other topics.

Most of the hours of the discipline are allocated to the independent work of students in educational institutions, it is important to organize this activity so that, in the end, students acquire the necessary information for communicating in a foreign language. In this case, the teacher is assigned the task of clearly defining the language lesson and its content in each case. Based on the laws described above, it can be noted that only active, designed forms of work in foreign language classes can contribute to the implementation of professionally oriented education: learning topics and vocabulary in the chosen field, Read-minimally professional articles with the help of at.

In reality, the meaning of English has changed for students themselves, because they have more and more opportunities to participate in various language programs, listen to real news, read texts, communicate online with students from different countries. The communicative status of the language has changed in school, college and university, even in the teaching of children whose English takes only 4-5 modules and is not included in the list of general vocational subjects. Indeed, on the one hand, the change of political and social life is making more and more demands on both the teacher and the student, who must be active and mobile in the

translation of socio-cultural experience and accumulated knowledge. Therefore, teachers strive to integrate all required educational technologies in educational institutions with special attention to English language classes, communicative competence and person-oriented.

Different technologies require different knowledge from the teacher on the methodical design of all the structurally selected and integrated stages of the lesson, in this article we will pay special attention to the project activity, which is one of the required and, in our opinion, interesting communication technologies.

The modern realities of teaching a foreign language among Russian-speaking students allow to build all stages of the lesson, taking into account the approach of teaching methods to the modern educational and informational needs of university and high school students. This is an appeal to the communicative and practice-oriented teaching method to build the foreign language teaching process at the university and high school, in which the speech itself and the language materials required in the future professional life become the object of activity. In such classes, the main action of the teacher is the desire to involve all students in the language environment, to provide all students with language materials. An important aspect of this method is that the student can use various exercises in role-playing games, dialogues, preparing essays, working letters, and listening, thus stimulating all channels of perception of language information of modern students.

In this case, we suggest the following practice of organizing and systematizing language materials for students of non-language majors:

Stage 1-The teacher is a translator of language by teaching reading, building vocabulary, and presenting real or close texts for reading and comprehension.

Stage 2 - students' active actions under the guidance of a foreign language teacher, through a series of tasks aimed at understanding grammatical, lexical, phonetic and regional materials, in particular, through the audiovisual method of reading in classes and independent work.

3 level of language acquisition is related not only through reproductive student activities, but also through creating presentations, participating in mini-debates, student conferences, and trying to model speech dialogues based on memorizing speech clichés through direct communication with students, teachers, and volunteers . countries, language studied and online etc. promoting language communication and the role of language for students in general.

Perhaps the third level of language learning is carried out in part depending on the level of students in the group, the level of development of language tasks and the level of readiness of the teacher to implement similar practices among students of this category, but undoubtedly, even understanding the general educational program is beyond the reach of students. A partial attempt to bring communicative competence closer to the level of knowledge is also worthy of respect, and it is worth the effort.

Now we will try to analyze the possible stages of organizing and designing this method of active interaction in English lessons using specific examples of project activities with students.

These recommended methods for designing student project activities can be used in teaching any language subject as long as they meet the following requirements:

1. Students and teachers see the practical and theoretical-scientific significance and effectiveness of the work done;
2. The structural and careful design of all stages of work gradually reduces the role of the teacher and increases the independence and responsibility of students.

3. Use of all 4 linguistic aspects using increasingly new forms of student activity in foreign language classes.

In this case, we should talk about a comprehensive approach to the implementation of these types of tasks, as it is known that students learn more actively in a state of personal interest and without coercion, and experience a positive reaction of approval from their peers and teacher. In this case, students will not only have the opportunity to receive positive feedback, but also have the necessary research experience in working with information and media systems, websites, and language books and dictionaries, which will help them learn the language. is a method of expanding the real and actual level of mastery. Consequently, in such classes, students work more actively than in the traditional stages of class activities around the textbook and subject notebook.

Also, another form of project activity together with students can be elements of holding holidays and thematic lessons - quizzes, quests, festivals on creative competitions, traditions, food, culture of English-speaking countries, number contains information about the name. By observing the history, cultural characteristics and uniqueness of different nations during the celebration of the main events, students can not only supplement their ideas and compare them with the traditions of Uzbekistan and Uzbek-speaking countries, but also cultural Linguistically, they can fully master vocabulary, grammar, and phonetics.

Concluding the analysis of modern contradictions in foreign language teaching in the non-linguistic environment of higher education, it should be noted that educational literature, library equipment fully meet the requirements of teaching methodology, taking into account the use of new information technologies does not answer. Therefore, the teacher himself must find and constantly develop additional tasks for a multi-level student, variable exercises, which are always based on the specifics of the direction in which the language is taught and new for students. improves their methodological and pedagogical level, paying attention to the desire to search for active activities.

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